

Effect of Pricing Policy on Financial Performance of Brewery Firms in Nigeria.

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Abstract: *The main objective of this study was to ascertain the effect of pricing policy on financial performance in selected brewery firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to; ascertain the extent to which cost-based pricing affect return on asset of listed brewery firms in Nigeria and determine the degree to which competition-based pricing affect profit after tax of listed brewery firms in Nigeria. The study used ex-post facto research design. Secondary data was used and the population of this study consisted of all the five brewery firms listed on the floor of the Nigerian Exchange Group as at December 2023. The sample size of the study consisted of five (5) listed brewery firms in Nigeria. The hypotheses were tested using Pooled Ordinary Least Square (OLS) Model. It was found that cost-based pricing policy (CBP) had a significant positive effect on return on assets (ROA) of listed brewery firms in Nigeria. This is evidenced by the co-efficient value of 0.482521 accompanied by a probability value of 0.02134 which is below 5% conventional level of significance and Competitive-based pricing policy (CMBP) had a significant negative effect on profit after tax (PAT) of listed brewery firms in Nigeria. This is substantiated by the coefficient value of -0.002086 accompanied by a probability value of 0.0303 which is below 5%. It was concluded that cost-based pricing and competitive-based pricing policies significantly affect organizational performance of brewery firms in Nigeria especially in terms of return on asset and profit after tax. It was recommended that brewery firms in Nigeria should continue to adopt cost-based pricing and competitive-based pricing in order to improve their return on assets and profit after tax.*

Keywords: *Pricing Policy, financial performance, cost-based pricing and competitive based pricing.*

INTRODUCTION

Background

Pricing policy is a crucial decision for any business organization; a company's survival and profitability depend on its pricing decisions as the price is the only element in the marketing mix that produces revenue and consequently generates profit. As perceived by Kotler and Armstrong (2018), effective pricing management is a vital tool for a business to achieve its targets and may help it to meet long-term organizational goals. The marketing mix is a set of marketing tools that a business uses to sell products or services to its target customers (Lake, 2021). Therefore, a reasonable price can only be established after other marketing mix elements have been reviewed. The ultimate purpose of any price choice is to enable an organization to fulfill its objectives, and these may vary depending on the nature of the firm. For profit-oriented firms, the main aim is profit maximization, and this may be strongly affected by pricing practices.

Kotler & Armstrong (2010), a company's survival and profitability depend upon its pricing decisions thus price is the only element in the marketing mix that produces revenue and thus ensures profitability. The price adopted by firms must be able to cover all costs in the long run as well as to leave a profit margin to reward management and other shareholders. Organizations may accomplish profit maximization through many means: cost reduction, boosting market share, entering new markets, and establishing high pricing, among others. In the strategic management school of thinking, an organization's business-level strategy may focus on cost leadership or product differentiation as strategies for attaining its objectives. The cost leadership strategy is when a company aims to lower costs to levels below that of its rivals, whereas the product differentiation strategy is targeted at distinguishing a product from other, comparable items on the market.

Pricing policies are a set of standard procedures used by a firm to set wholesale or retail prices for its products or services (Atuma, 2013). On the other hand, Pricing is the measure by which customers perceive the value of a product, and it greatly impacts brand selection among competing alternatives (Shipley & Jobber, 2001). This responsibility to adopt a price that will be profitable, cover costs, and reward solely depends on management. This is because prices are not determined through arbitrary means but through thoughtful and calculated systems that will keep the company profitable and rewarding. This, therefore, requires management to engage all the necessary factors to determine the most profitable price.

Pricing policy, if properly planned and evaluated, can be a competitive weapon in a dynamic market. It is therefore evident that an important managerial responsibility is setting and adopting the most advantageous pricing policy. Irrespective of the importance of effective pricing decisions and policies, it is quite unfortunate that many firms are still mismanaging

pricing causing lots of money and anticipated profits to be unexplored and wasted. This could be attributed to the constant economic challenges faced by firms.

Hilton & Platt (2014), the market forces of supply and demand as well as the cost of production have a significant effect on determining prices, also other variables that also influence pricing decisions, include the manufacturer pricing objectives, the economic situation, competitors and the availability of close substitutes. Numerous firms especially in developing countries like Nigeria still struggle to identify the elements that impact price, even though pricing is a core strategic choice. This incapacity of the management of various firms to make an effective pricing decision has been linked to the collapse of numerous businesses. Thus, adequate and effective pricing decisions are important in an organization's marketing mix and competitive strategy. In 2011, at a financial crisis inquiry committee interview, Warren Buffet stated, "Price power is the single most important decision in evaluating a business. A prosperous company can increase prices and yet turn a profit while holding onto its customers.

Most enterprises today are faced with the problem of how to maximize shareholders' profits, while also remaining competitive and relevant in a constantly evolving market. The drive to increase earnings and keep a place in the market puts a variety of duties on managers who are saddled with the key responsibility of making adequate business decisions to make sure that this goal is achieved. And one of these key responsibilities is to make pricing decisions and policies. Currently, pricing policy and its effect on the performance of firms particularly in developing countries like Nigeria have not garnered much scholarly attention, despite a recent wave of interest. Based on this premise the study to ascertain the effectiveness of pricing policy on the profit planning of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria becomes imperative.

Statement of the Problem

The volatility of the business environment especially in developing countries ranging from continuous rise in inflation rate, unstable exchange rate, and forces of demand and supply, has been a cause of major concern to various industries today. Most manufacturing companies in developing countries like Nigeria are currently faced with the challenges of managing the ripple-down effect of these macroeconomic variables on their business operation. They are also faced with the problem of maintaining competitive advantage, retaining current and prospective customers and profitability through adequate pricing strategy. Setting prices remains a complex decision for most companies. These challenges mainly can be attributed to the incapacity of management of various firms especially in developing countries, to make optimum pricing decisions and policies in their business, even though pricing is a fundamental strategic decision. Though many organizations still struggle

to identify the factors that influence prices and this has been linked to the collapse of numerous businesses.

Many variables come into play to ensure the price is affordable to customers and satisfies stakeholders' profit interest the difficulties in setting prices result from the sensitivity of consumers' demands regarding the price change. A slightly insignificant change at the wrong time may lead to a drastic fall in market shares and profit. According to Nagle and Müller (2017), owing to marketing globalization and increasing technological changes, the number of competitors and new sources of value for customers has increased which did not necessarily lead to rises in profit for the producers. Therefore, there is a need for firms to adopt an effective pricing policy as a vital tool for a business to achieve its long-term organizational goals. Pricing policy, if properly planned and evaluated, can be a competitive strategy in a dynamic market. It is therefore evident that an important managerial responsibility is setting and adopting the most advantageous pricing policy to stay above its competitors and enhance profitability.

Most small business owners especially in developing countries like Nigeria lack the knowledge and skills of basic marketing ingredients, such as marketing research, market segmentation, and market planning and control, which thereafter leads to poor quality products, unawareness of competition, poor distribution, and poor pricing methods. The poor pricing methods thereafter lead to poor product pricing, which will eventually affect sales (demand) and finally the profit of the business. In developing countries, with low income and high levels of poverty, a company that wants to succeed should offer its product at the price the consumers can bear. But often, small manufacturers set prices of their products arbitrarily without regard to consumer characteristics in the environment (Ayozie 2008). Based on these major concerns it becomes important to conduct this study to address the pending issues surrounding pricing policy and profit planning on listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study was to ascertain the effect of pricing policy on financial performance of brewery firms in Nigeria. The specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. Ascertain the extent to which cost-based pricing affect return on asset of listed brewery firms in Nigeria.
- ii. Determine the degree to which competition-based pricing affect profit after tax of listed brewery firms in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Price and Pricing Policy

Pricing policy refers to the policy by which a company determines the wholesale and retail prices for its products or services (Shivam 2019). In the ever-dynamic business environment firms are faced with the challenges of covering their daily operational costs, staying over their competitors, and breaking even in the long run. Atuma (2013), every business entity is set up with the primary objective of making profits and several considerations underlying their profit motive come to bear in determining the pricing of their goods between associated parties (Kotler & Armstrong 2010; Nebo & Onyeke, 2021; Ejiomueme & Nebo, 2021; Britannica, 2021).

Cost-based Pricing

This is the oldest and most straightforward (mostly) method of setting prices. The main idea is for a firm to develop its product, determine the cost incurred in production, fix the price based on the cost, and convince buyers of the value of the goods and/or services. An article by Ihsanul (2020), explained that in a mechanized company that processes a product, determining the selling price can be tricky due to the large number of expenses determining factor of the selling price (Nebo & Onyeke, 2021; Ejiomueme & Nebo, 2021).

Competitive-based Pricing Policy

Competitive pricing is the process of selecting strategic price points to best take advantage of a product based on the market relative to the competition. Competitive pricing is generally used once a price for a product t service has reached a level of equilibrium most brewery companies will carry out competitive pricing (Nebo & Onyeke, 2021; Ejiomueme & Nebo, 2021).

Financial Performance

Financial performance has been defined by various scholars. Trivedi (2010) defined it as the process of measuring the results of a firm's policies and operations in monetary terms. He further explains that financial performance is a way of measuring the overall health of an organization over some time and it is used in making comparisons across industries or to compare industries or sectors. For this study Return on Asset and Net profit after tax (PAT) was used as a proxy for measuring firm performance and profitability.

Return on Assets

Suwamo (2004), Return on Assets (ROA) is a type of return on investment metric that measures the profitability of a business to its total assets. This ratio indicates how well a company is performing by comparing the profit (net income) it's generating to the capital it's

invested in assets. The higher the return, the more productive and efficient management is in utilizing economic resources.

Profit After Tax

Profit after tax (PAT) is said to be the net profit available for the shareholders after paying all the expenses and taxes by the business unit. This can mathematically be depicted as $PAT = \text{Net profit before tax} - \text{Total tax expense}$.

Conceptual Framework

Here we discussed the connection link between dependent and independent variables, meanwhile, independent known as pricing policy decomposed into cost-based pricing and competitive-based pricing while financial performance remains dependent variables which was decomposed into return on asset and profit after tax. Comprehensive diagrammatical illustration was demonstrated below;

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Model

Depicting the Relationship Between Pricing Policy and Financial Performance of Brewery Firms in Nigeria.

Source: Ejioneme and Nebo (2021) and Nebo and Onyeke (2021) and Trivedi (2010)

Theoretical Framework

This study was underpinned by the three theories (Game pricing and Arbitrage pricing theory) adopted in this work, because of their various relevance to the subject matter.

Game Pricing Theory

The game pricing theory was propounded by John von Neumann and economist Oskar Morgenstern in the 1940s and was developed extensively by many other researchers and scholars in the 1950s. There are two key assumptions underlying this theory: the first assumption is that each player in the market acts on self-interest. They pursue well-defined exogenous objectives, i.e. they are rational. They understand and seek to maximize their payoff functions. While, the second assumption is that in choosing a plan of action (strategy),

a player considers the potential responses/reactions of other players. Game theory is a powerful tool that can be applied to various aspects of business, including pricing strategies. In the context of pricing, game theory helps businesses understand how their pricing decisions can impact their competitors and ultimately their profitability.

Arbitrage Pricing Theory

The Arbitrage Pricing Theory (APT) was developed primarily by Ross (1977). Arbitrage pricing theory is a financial model used to determine the appropriate price of an asset by considering its expected return on its risk. This theory suggests that the price of an asset/product should reflect the expected return based on its risk characteristics, and any deviations from this fair price can be exploited through arbitrage opportunities. The key assumption of arbitrage pricing theory is that investors are rational and will take advantage of any mispricing in the market. By identifying and exploiting this mispricing, investors can earn riskless profits and help bring the price of the asset back in line with its fair value. Arbitrage pricing theory is widely used in the financial industry to price a variety of assets, including stocks, bonds, and derivatives. It provides a framework for understanding how different factors, such as interest rates, inflation, and market volatility, can impact the price of an asset.

Empirical Review

Elumaro, Okwo, Nwoha and Eze (2024) studied assets management and financial performance of listed consumer goods manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The aim of this study was to evaluate the effect of assets management on financial performance of the Nigeria's consumer goods manufacturing company. The study adopted an ex-post facto design. The study found that assets turnover ratio and assets tangibility have significant positive and negative effect on return on assets with t-statistics respectively whereas intellectual assets ratio exerted a non-significant positive effect on return on assets.

Hartiya, Fahmi and Sirojuzilam (2024) conducted a study on the influence of leverage, profitability, and price share to return share in manufacturing companies on the IDX with company value as intervening variables. Results study showing that only profitability and price share yang can increase stock returns something company manufacturing on the indonesian stock exchange.

Ting, Tsan-Ming and Tai-Chiu (2024) examined competitive pricing and product strategies in the presence of consumers' social comparisons in United Kingdom. This result highlights that relative to reducing the quality difference between the two firms, the product-line extension strategy can be a more effective way for the firms to manage consumers' social comparisons.

Tanyi (2021) conducted a study on pricing policy and profitability level of an organization. The research adopted a qualitative research design as the theoretical approach was adopted to analyze the study. The findings of the study revealed that the effectiveness of pricing policy and price planning has a significant influence on the profitability level of organizations. Nafuna, *et al* (2019) investigated the role of competitive advantage in moderating the association that exists among pricing strategies and financial success in Uganda's private elementary schools. The findings show that the competitive edge mediates the association between pricing strategies and financial performance to some extent (it is not a strong but a partial mediation).

Gap in Literature

Based on the empirical studies reviewed it has been discovered that studies on the effectiveness of pricing policy and performance are relatively scanty and focused mainly on developed countries, there are only a few studies on this topic were done in developing countries like Nigeria. Again, all the existing studies were done in other firms not related to brewery industry. Therefore, this work filled this gap by studying the effect of pricing policy on the financial performance of Brewery sector which has been neglected by other researchers. Based on the empirical review, It was discovered that little or no recent work has been done on the subject matter, and existing works neglected the effect of cost-based and competitive-based pricing policies on return on assets (ROA) and profit after tax (PAT) respectively, this study introduced these two variables to fill this gap. This study served as the latest update to the existing literature, by examining the effect of pricing policy on financial performance of brewery firms in Nigeria from 2017 to 2023.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study adopted an *ex-post facto* research design to examine the effect of pricing policy on the financial performance of listed brewery firms in Nigeria.

Nature and Sources of Data

The study employed cross-sectional data (secondary data) of published variables as extracted from the financial statements of the brewer/distiller consumer goods sector of manufacturing firms in Nigeria as contained in their annual reports from 2017-2023.

Population of the Study

The population of this study consists of all the five (Nigerian Brewery Plc. Golden Guinea Nigeria Plc, International Brewery Plc, Guinness Nigeria Plc and Champions Brewery Plc) listed breweries in Nigeria extracted from Nigerian Exchange Group (NXG), as at December 2023.

Sample Size

The sample size of the study consists of five (5) listed breweries namely Nigerian Brewery Plc. Golden Guinea Nigeria Plc, International Brewery Plc, Guinness Nigeria Plc and Champions Brewery Plc).

Sampling Technique

A judgmental sampling technique was adopted to select the sample element of the study which consists of the listed brewery firms in the brewery/distiller sub-sector.

Model Specification

This study adopted a panel regression model on a cross-sectional study of 5 firms along with previous theoretical and empirical specifications to examine data spanning the period 2017-2023. Following the hypotheses earlier formulated, a panel regression model is formulated to capture the Pooled, Fixed, and Random effect of pricing policy on financial performance. This model help to achieve the objectives earlier stated expressly.

The apriori expectation (i,e, $\beta_1 \geq 0$)

$${}_2(\text{LogCMBPPit}) + \mu_i \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

FP = Financial Performance proxied by Return on Asset

CBP = Cost-Based Pricing

CMBP = Competitive-Based Pricing

μ = Error Term

α = Constant

β = Regression coefficient

t = Time at Present

t-i = Time at lag i, i-1,2

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_{it} + \alpha_2 Z_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_i (\text{LogCBPit}) + \alpha$$

Description of Variables

i. Return on Assets (ROA)

ROA measures the firm’s assets profitability after meeting all expenses and taxes. It measures the profit of the firm after tax for each naira “N” invested in assets (Ross, Westerfield, Jaffe, & Jordan 2015). The ROA formula is: $\text{ROA} = \text{Net Income} / \text{Average Assets}$.

ii. Profit After Tax (PAT)

Profit after tax (PAT) is said to be the net profit available for the shareholders after paying all the expenses and taxes *by* the business unit. $\text{PAT} = \text{Net profit before tax} - \text{Total tax expense}$.

Independent Variables

i. Cost-Based Pricing

Cost pricing involves factoring in various costs incurred during the production process of a product before fixing a selling price. This will be measured by the Natural Logarithm of Cost of Sales (COS).

ii. Competitive-Based Pricing

This pricing policy presents a situation where firms set their prices by determining what competing firms are charging. Then the firm examines its products or services after which it sets either a higher price or lower price depending on what advantage can be derived by the firm.

Methods of Data Analyses

The panel regression model took the form of the Fixed Effects Model, Random Effects Model, and Pooled Ordinary Least Square (OLS) model to establish the most appropriate regression with the highest explanatory power that is better suited to the data set employed in the study. The Pooled Ordinary Least Square (POLS) was used in the first instance. However, because of the weaknesses associated with it, The Fixed Effects Model (FEM) and Random Effect Model (REM) were adopted to capture the performance of the firms considered in the study. The usual identification tests the Housman's Chi-square statistics for testing whether the Fixed Effects model estimator is an appropriate alternative to the Random Effects model will be also computed for each model.

A Prior Expectations

It is expected that pricing policy variables adopted for this study will have a significant effect on the return on asset and profitability of the studied firms. **Decision rule**, Reject the null hypothesis (**H₀**) if the p-value of the model is less than (<) 0.05, otherwise, reject the Alternate hypothesis (**H₁**) and accept the null hypothesis (**H₀**).

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSES

Data Presentation

Data presented in Appendix 1

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics

	CBP	CMBP	ROA	PAT
Mean	2.511008	2.088235	0.047508	56772286
Median	1.152208	2.000000	0.042953	13426125
Std. Dev.	4.544908	1.400598	0.031844	1.071208
Skewness	3.272209	-0.091343	0.704397	2.638204
Kurtosis	13.43507	1.791849	2.812368	10.15879
Jarque-Bera	195.9717	2.115089	2.861534	112.0424
Probability	0.000000	0.347308	0.239125	0.000000

Sources: Author Computation using E-Views Software

The table above shows the result of the basic descriptive statistics summary report of measures of central tendency comprising the “mean, median, and standard deviation which are the measure of spread and variation from the mean. The Kurtosis is a measure of the level of peakedness or flatness, the Skewness is a measure of the degree of departure from symmetry, while the probability of jaque-bera explains the normality of the data distributions. From the descriptive analysis, it is observed that the variables are normally distributed.

Panel Unit Root Test

Most cross-sectional and time-series data in the econometric analysis are mostly nonstationary (Engle and Granger, 1987), Therefore to ensure the reliability of our analysis the summarized unit root test model of Phillips-Perron (1988) was adopted to test the stability properties of the variables.

Table 4.2 Summary of Phillips-Perron Unit Root Test

Variables	PP - Fisher Chi-square (Prob)	Inference
LogCBP	21.7376*** (0.0054)	1(1)
LogCMBP	11.1853** (0.0017)	1(1)
LogROA	34.3539*** (0.0002)	1(1)
LogPAT	22.6879*** (0.0120)	1(1)

Source: Researcher’s Computation using E-view

*The p-values are smaller than 1%, the null hypothesis is rejected, and we conclude that the variables series are stationary. ***, **, * mean significant at 1%, 5% and 10% respectively. P-Values are in parenthesis. ** Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic Chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality. The panel unit root results displayed in Table 4.2 show that the studied variables both the dependent, independent, and control variables attained stability at the first level (1) order of integration. This indicates that the data is fit to be used for analysis with a lower possibility of producing a spurious result. That is to say, the result obtained from this study can be relied on with utmost confidence.*

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

H₀: Cost-based pricing does not have a significant positive effect on the return on assets of listed brewery firms in Nigeria.

$$\text{LogROA}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 (\text{LogCBP}_{it}) + \mu_{it} \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Table 4.3 Panel Regression Result for Hypothesis One Dependent Variable: LogROA

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LogCBP	0.482521	0.178511	8.985856	0.02134
C	0.022990	0.022621	1.016323	0.13237
Weighted Statistics				
<i>R-Squared</i>	0.508139	Durbin-Watson stat		2.419475
F-Statistics	22.50894	Prob(F-statistic)		0.027496

Source: Author’s Computation using E-view

The result in Table 4.3 above showed the estimation of the effect of cost-based pricing on return on the return on assets of listed brewery firms in Nigeria. The result shows that cost based pricing (CPB) has a positive significant effect on return on asset (ROA) with a coefficient of 0.482523 and 0.253147 and probability value of 0.02134 and 0.01361 respectively. The R² of 0.51% measures the goodness of fit of the panel regression line model also showing the model reliability and the variation in the dependent variable accounted for by the independent variable, with an unexplained variation of 49%. The F- statistic of 22.50894 and the matching probability value of 0.00027496 infer that the model is all inclusive and is positive and statistically significant for reliable analysis. The Durbin Watson

Statistics of 2. 419475 rules out the possible existence of first-order positive autocorrelation. The estimated regression result is reliable for a valid inference on the effect of the independent variables on the return on asset (ROA) of listed brewery firms in Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two

H₀: Competition-based pricing does not have a significant positive effect on the profit after tax of listed brewery firms in Nigeria.

$$\text{LogROA}_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 (\text{LogCMBP}_{it}) + \mu_{it} \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Table 4.4 Panel Regression Result for Hypothesis Two Dependent Variable: LogROA

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LogCMBP	-0.002086	0.023488	5.088829	0.0303
C	0.022990	0.022621	1.016323	0.3237
Weighted Statistics				
<i>R-Squared</i>	0.658139	Durbin-Watson stat		2.281541
F-Statistics	12.57594	Prob(F-statistic)		0.013496

Source: Author’s Computation using E-view

The result in Table 4.4 above showed the estimation of the effect of competition-based pricing on the profit after tax of listed brewery firms in Nigeria. The result shows that competition-based pricing (CMBP) have a negative significant effect on profit after tax with a coefficient of -0.120860 and -3.392311 and probability values of 0.0303 and 0.0116 respectively. The R² of approximately 0.66% measures the goodness of fit of the panel regression line model also shows the model reliability and the variation in the dependent variable accounted for by the independent variable, with an unexplained variation of 34%. The Fstatistic of 12.57594 and the matching probability value of 0.013496 infer that the model is all inclusive and is positive and statistically significant for reliable analysis. The Durbin Watson Statistics of 2.28154 rules out the possible existence of first-order positive autocorrelation. The estimated regression result is reliable for a valid inference on the influence of the independent variables on the profit after tax listed brewery firms in Nigeria.

Summary of Findings

The findings emanated from the study were as follows:

1. Cost-based pricing policy (CBP) had a significant positive effect on return on assets (ROA) of listed brewery firms in Nigeria. This is evidenced by the co-efficient value of 0.482521 accompanied by a probability value of 0.02134 which is below 5% conventional level of significance.
2. Competitive-based pricing policy (CMBP) had a significant negative effect on profit after tax (PAT) of listed brewery firms in Nigeria. This is substantiated by the coefficient value of -0.002086 accompanied by a probability value of 0.0303 which is below 5%.

Conclusion

Findings of the study suggest that a holistic approach to pricing, which considers multiple factors and adapts to changing market conditions, is essential for maximizing profitability. By adopting such an approach, businesses can optimize their pricing strategies, stay competitive, and achieve sustained financial success. The implications of this study are relevant for companies across various industries, and our findings can inform pricing decisions and contribute to the development of effective pricing strategies.

Recommendations

Based on the above findings on the subject matter the following recommendations are made:

- i. Brewery firms in Nigeria should adopt cost-based pricing to achieve their positive return on assets.
- ii. Brewery firms should also adopt in competitive pricing policy to improve their profit after tax (PAT),

Contributions to Knowledge

This study contributed to existing knowledge on this topic by introducing return on asst and profit after tax in the study and also deviated from previous studies in scope by focusing mainly on the brewery sub-sector of the manufacturing firms considering the nature of their product and the competition level involved in that industry. This study contributed to existing knowledge by methodology the introduction of the augmented- toda Yamamoto causality test away from the conventional Granger causality used by most researchers has opened new study evidence as the Toda Yamamoto estimate is used irrespective of the order of integration of the variables 1(0), 1(1) or 1(2) no previous study on the topic has embraced the superiority of the Toda-Yamamoto causality test.

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